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IPHE would like to urge upon members and other professionals, practicing engineers, consultants in the Public Health Engineering field to come forward and submit articles/technical papers as many in numbers to promote disseminating various challenges, experiences, good practices and emerging technologies like ozonation as treatment and disinfection, advanced oxidation, nano-bubbles technology in water treatments, safe disposal of water treatment sludges including safe handling and disposal of Disinfectant Byproducts (DBPs), etc. A great emphasis is to be given on the importance of water quality monitoring and management, wastewater treatment and safe disposal, solid waste safe handling, transportation, treatments and safe disposal, sewerage and drainage, sanitation and management, plastic waste management, climate resilient infrastructure, health hazards including preventive and curative management by improving upon the systems of safe delivery of various services including services during Manmade and Godly acts emergency situations in the public health engineering field to ensure safety and quality life on this planet.

Sri Himanshu Prasad, *Editor*

Dear Readers!

There were several water-related events in October - November 2024, including: Global Handwashing Day, Universal Children's Day, World Toilet Day, etc.

Like each year on October 15, 2024, the "Global Handwashing Day" was celebrated to raise awareness about the importance of washing hands with soap and water. Clean hands continue to be our frontline defence against the spread of infections, illnesses and harmful germs. Whether in households, hospitals, schools, or workplaces, handwashing with soap and water plays a critical role in creating safer environments and better health outcomes. The Universal Children's Day is celebrated annually on November 20th. The 2024 theme, "Listen to the Future" will focus on today's global challenges that are threatening children's futures.

World Toilet Day 2024: Ensuring Safely Managed Sanitation for Cities—World Toilet Day is celebrated annually on 19 November to inspire action to tackle the global sanitation crisis and help achieve SDG 6, which promises sanitation for all by 2030. The theme for World Toilet Day 2024, is "Toilets – A Place for Peace," which highlighted the importance of sanitation and sustainable solutions. It's main focus is on giving emphasis on safe lively toilets that improves public health, reduces infant mortality, and empowers women and girls. Towards this endeavour, the Clean Toilet Campaign 2024 has been launched on the 19th November 2024 stressing that cleanliness is ongoing and urged stakeholders to maintain and repair toilets for safe sanitation.

For sure it is becoming ardent tasks for the Public Health Engineers and experts to provide guidance to the community on the afore-mentioned services so as to ensure women empowerment, improve community health and reduce infant mortality. Mere sloganeering may not be enough to promote achieving SDG Goal 6.1 and 6.2. Emphasis should be on the importance of complimenting and supplementing safe water and safe wastewater management including recycling used water for various non-potable use for water replenishment and mitigating water scarcity. The water circular economy in this regard plays very important role which further invites attention to manage rain water and storm water drainage to improve ecology, environment and natural water bodies.

Further, there has been advancement and development to treat the wastewater and make it innovatively useful to reuse for Agricultural, Industrial (for cooling purpose) and other allied services apart from recharging ground water and meeting other non-potable needs to the extent that will balance the natural recycling without causing any hinderances and blocks including any land and water contamination.

Also, due to land constraints there is new trend of multistorey wastewater treatment plants being developed and constructed successfully. We the Public Health Engineers could prove to be the catalysts to such endeavours at large to create safe environment and make community healthy.

Best wishes

Himanshu Prasad
Editor, IPHE, India

JOURNAL OF THE INSTITUTION OF PUBLIC HEALTH ENGINEERS, INDIA

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(A) Contribution : Papers based on practical experience, case studies and popular issues related to Public Health Engineering/Environmental Engineering are particularly welcome.

Research findings related to above may also be sent.

(B) **Length** : Not more than 3000 words all inclusive (i.e. space for tables, figures etc duly considered as included) - preferably within 2500 words.

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Efficient Design of a Municipal Solid Waste Management Network: Insights from Jodhpur

Anirudh Sharma*

Assistant Professor, Dept. of Civil Engineering,
J.I.E.T Engineering College, Jodhpur,
Rajasthan, India, sanirudh1995@gmail.com

Dr. A. N. Modi

Professor and Head, Dept. of Civil Engineering,
M.B.M. Engineering College, M.B.M. University,
Jodhpur, Rajasthan, India

Abstract:

Waste management is a crucial component of urban development and is increasingly significant in developing countries. Landfills, first established for the purpose of managing hazardous waste and later remodelled into sanitary landfills, have been the most often used method for managing municipal solid waste on a global scale. Nevertheless, the traditional configuration of landfills not just falls short in meeting the requirements of waste management but also falls short in effectively maximizing resource recovery as well as energy production. The current work introduces a modified design for a partly designed landfill system, which is centred on theoretical considerations. An analysis was conducted on the potential of Jodhpur municipal solid waste for energy production and resource use. The investigation revealed that the system, after undergoing design modifications, has the capacity to produce 0.134 million tons of landfill gas (equal to 0.145 MT of coal) from 1 years' worth of solid waste. Additionally, this has the potential to retrieve resources with a value of US\$1.825 million annually.

Keywords: Design of landfills; LFG (landfill gas); MSW (municipal solid waste); generation of energy; GHG (greenhouse gas).

1. Introduction:

The creation of solid trash is a notable outcome of socio-economic activities. Different nations have varying a description of solid waste. Nevertheless, the majority of definitions for municipal solid waste encompass the garbage produced by the industrial sector, commercial enterprises, families, institutions, and municipal services. The production of urban as well as municipal solid waste is directly correlated with the rising population and rapid urbanization, as well as the rise of industry, as discussed by Singh and Sharma (2002) and Minghua et al. (2009). Currently, waste is being generated at a higher pace than other environmental pollutants, such as greenhouse gasses. The reference is Hoornweg et al., 2013. India, the country with the second highest population in the world, had an increase in urbanization between 27.82% in 2001 to 31.17% in 2011. The growing population is placing considerable pressure on the need for housing, food, and various other natural assets (Manser and Keeling 1996; Cointreau 2006a, b; Kathiravale and MuhdYunus 2008).

The management of municipal solid waste (MSWM) is an essential service provided by the Urban Local Bodies (ULBs), The government of India, which is often overlooked. MSW (municipal solid waste) production and characteristics may change across several geographical levels, such as nations, states, cities, as well as among different areas of the same city.

The per capita daily production rates for MSW (municipal solid waste) in Indian localities range from 0.3 to 0.6 kilogram. According to Pattnaik and Reddy (2010), the annual increase in the amount of Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) generated is projected to

* **Corresponding Author:** Anirudh Sharma
Sanirudh1995@gmail.com

be approximately 1.33% per person. Developing countries, like India, are facing challenges in creating a competent and flexible system for effectively handling municipal solid waste (MSW) for the public. They often face challenges in attaining this objective because to a deficiency in a proper method for gathering, technical expertise, and sufficient financial assets (Sujauddin et al., 2008; Guerrero et al., 2013). Municipalities dedicate a substantial percentage of their economic resources to the retrieval of municipal solid trash (both primary and secondary) from different locations within their jurisdiction. As a result, there is a certain amount of funding allocated for the management of this waste. Developing countries dedicate less than 0.5% of their per capita gross national product (GNP) to the management of MSW (municipal solid waste) services (What a waste 1999). In addition, MSWM plans are greatly impacted by legal, political, socio-cultural, and institutional factors.

In their study, Rajendiran et al. (2012) emphasized the roles and involvement of several government agencies in managing municipal solid waste (MSWM), including the Ministry of Agriculture, the Ministry of New and Renewable Energy, the Ministry of Environment and Forests, the Ministry of Urban Development, and the Ministry of Non-Conventional Energy Sources. Furthermore, the involvement of both the formal and informal sectors might potentially enhance the governance for municipal solid waste (Sharholy et al., 2008). An all-encompassing solution, such as the notion of ISWM (integrated solid waste management), is required, along with a resolute endeavor from all sectors of society. Otherwise, it will persistently have a detrimental influence on the three fundamental aspects of sustainability: the

economy, the environment, and society. The exponential growth of human population and urbanization results in an increase in environmental apprehensions. Efficiently handling municipal solid waste (MSW) is essential for tackling the growing urban issues. The economy has a substantial influence on the generation of rubbish, especially municipal solid waste (MSW). Municipal solid waste (MSW) is distinct from other forms of solid waste, such as industrial waste, hazardous waste, as well as medical waste, since it originates from a wide range of sources. Local communities along with regulatory agencies have a considerable issue in collecting and disposing of non-point/area sources. According to CES (2000), impoverished countries have a minimum per capita waste generation rate of 300 grams per capita per day. However, due to changes in living conditions and the influence of western consumerism, it is expected that there will be a continuous rise in solid waste output (CES, 2000; IIT, 1997). The increase in the generation of solid waste not only causes environmental degradation but also results in the major loss of natural resources, which is not well documented (Parikh and Parikh, 1997).

The management of municipal solid waste (MSW) involves many separate phases, such as collection, transportation, processing, and disposal. The main method used is land disposal. Developed countries have created and well-maintained landfills (DOE/EIA, 1999). Nevertheless, in developing countries like as India, the existence of well built and efficiently operated landfills is uncommon. Garbage is disposed of in open landfills, resulting in substantial environmental harm and the exhaustion of renewable resources (Parikh and Parikh, 1997). Present landfill designs in developed countries primarily

prioritize the final disposal of waste, albeit with limited attention paid to the management of the associated gas emissions (EIP, 1999; Johennessen, 1999). These design procedures did not have a distinct focus on managing waste in relation to the use of natural resources. Notwithstanding the existence of numerous landfills in the United States that are outfitted with gas recovery systems, their establishment employed conventional approaches, which consequently led to a significantly diminished LFG output (LMOP-USEPA, 1996). The primary criteria for landfill design are on the safe and appropriate disposal of waste. Nonetheless, there is a deficiency in the design aimed at improving the efficiency of gas production as well as its collection. A new and customized approach to planning landfill systems incorporating gas recovery has been developed expressly for the conditions in India, taking into account the expected rise in waste output in developing countries and the existence of established gas recovery technology. India's waste management infrastructure is deficient in terms of adequate landfills, leading to a reliance on open dumps, which is in stark contrast to the practices of affluent countries. Currently, the Central Government is requiring the construction of landfills with suitable design, making this new method a timely and important undertaking. This design is especially tailored for the establishment of new landfill sites and will not be appropriate for retrofitting existing dumpsites. Landfills are engineered to maximize gas generation rates, which leads to faster generation of landfill gas (LFG) and also reduces the required land area. The LFG yield and energy values were estimated by the use of functional models derived from theoretical considerations.

2. Objectives

The present study seeks to provide an enhanced design methodology for landfill systems including gas recovery alternatives. Furthermore, it aims to assess the energy production capacity of MSW (municipal solid waste, Jodhpur under this specific scenario.

3. Present scenario in Jodhpur

Jodhpur, Rajasthan's second-largest city, is a famous tourist destination. The population of the city of 10,33,918 people, with a density of population of 11,210 people per square kilometres, according to the 2011 census. The daily anticipated municipal solid waste generation rate has risen dramatically over the previous few decades, with a present rate of around 450gm/person/day.

The current estimated population of 2022 is 1,548,048 people, which amounts to 696.62 MT of solid waste each day in Jodhpur.

3.1 Solid Waste Generations

The solid waste is gathered from many locations across Jodhpur. Some of these areas include Sabji Mandi, Fruit Mandi, K. M., the Airforce, the Army, the Railway, M.D.M., UMMAID House, M.G.H., RSRTC, B.S.F., AIIMS, LUCID, RIICO, JNVU, meat waste, hotel trash, M. S. B., NNJ, and door-to-door rubbish collections. During the three months of February, March, along with April 2021, the town produced around 16,414.20 metric tons, 15,781.39 metric tons, and 14,774.02 metric tons respectively. This translates to an average daily production of 586.22 metric tons, 509.07 metric tons, and 492.4 metric tons, as seen in Table 1.

3.2 Solid waste collection and transportation

JDA (Jodhpur Development Authority)

and Municipal Corporation of Jodhpur (MCJ) collect solid trash. Solid waste is picked at its source and transferred to three transfer locations by municipal vehicles and tractors. These cargo vans are manually loaded. Each tractor/mini truck used to work three to four

shifts a day, with an average daily travel distance of 30-35 kilometres. From the point of generation until disposal at dump sites, trash is handled manually in a variety of ways. Table 2 contains information about transfer stations.

TABLE 1 : February-April 2021 solid waste generation on a monthly basis. (MT/month) (Source JMC, Jodhpur)

Locality	Solid waste for February 2021 (MT/month)	Solid waste for March 2021 (MT/month)	Solid waste for April 2021 (MT/month)	Monthly average solid waste (MT)
Airforce area	77.94	85.49	68.07	77.17
Army area	270.53	294.68	291.53	285.58
Railway Station area	34.06	42.45	22.98	33.16
SabjiMandi	77.66	84.54	124.44	95.55
Fruit Mandi area	26.34	13.07	11.41	16.94
K.M. Area	43.38	79.11	52.83	58.44
RSRTC area	0.45	1.56	0	0.67
B. S. F.	23.39	48.49	31.05	34.31
AIIMS Area	23.94	20.02	28.38	24.11
M. D. M. Area	6.22	23.07	23.78	17.69
Ummaid House area	29.58	26.89	26.09	27.52
M. G. H. area	13.10	13.96	24.06	17.04
LUCID area	8.47	6.25	2.65	5.79
RIICO area	0	0	0	0
NVU area	0	0	0	0
Meat waste area	56.93	37.57	12.01	35.50
Hotel waste area	127.52	220.32	258.44	202.09
M. S. B. area	825.59	192.48	143.01	387.03
NNJ area	14287.32	14127.16	13174.77	13863.08
Door to Door	559.72	549.77	546.59	552.03
Total	16414.20	15781.39	14774.02	15656.54

Table.2 : Transfer stations of solid waste collection (Source JMC, Jodhpur)

Transfer Station	Land area used	Capacity
Near J J Sweet Home Pratap Nagar	80 m x 15 m	200 MT
Near Central Jail	75 m x 20 m	300 MT
Near CAZRI	75 m x 15 m	200 MT

(a)

(b)

(c)

**Figure-1 : Solid waste transfer station near
(a) Central Jail, (b) near J J Sweet Home Pratap Nagar & (c) CAZRI**

During the site visit, it was discovered that vehicles delivering rubbish were not covered with tarpaulin/plastic sheets. Figures 1. depict the current situation of solid waste collection and transportation at several transfer points in Jodhpur.

3.3 Solid waste disposal at the Dumping site, Keru:

The solid garbage from all three transfer points is then transported to a strategically placed disposal site in the hamlet of Keru (30 kilometres from Jodhpur Ratanada Airport) (Figure 2.)

3.3.1 Observations

- People often do not store garbage at the source, instead disposing of it in municipal bins, streets, open areas, sewers, and so on. Decomposable and non-decomposable trash are mixed together in the same containers. As a result, recyclable material is commonly found intermingled with rubbish on the streets, in municipal bins, and at disposal sites, where some of it is picked up by waste collectors.
- One of the key issues of solid waste management in India is proper trash segregation both at the source and at the disposal location.
- There are two types of storage bins: moveable and fixed. Moving bins are convenient for transportation, however they are not long-lasting.
- A huge amount of waste was found around multi-story buildings, large apartments, and practically all electric transformer towers across the city.
- The transport vans are manually loaded and operate 3 to 4 shifts per day. The

transportation system is out of sync with primary garbage collection and bulk trash storage facilities.

- The unregulated and improper disposal of trash contributes to an increase in the frequency of incidences of human health concerns.
- Despite the fact that most municipal garbage is dry, the amount of leachate generated is extremely little. During the monsoon season, however, it has the potential to pollute both ground and surface water resources.
- Waste is being dumped off at dump sites in an improper and haphazard way, which might lead to major environmental issues in the future.
- Keru's dumping site is protected by fences, an access road, and lighting. However, there was no monitoring facility to measure contamination or pesticides spray to control flies, etc., at the dumping sites.
- The dump facility gets around 450-500 tonnes of unprocessed MSW every day. The property is in the catchments of the Public Health and Engineering Department's (PHED) Kaylana water storage tank and the Irrigation Department's Umaid Sagar. The facility must be examined on a regular basis to ensure that it does not pose a health risk owing to pollution of surface water provided to Jodhpur for consumption.

The unsegregated waste thus collected passes through the flow line showed in Figure 4. No formal resource recovery exists in the JCGB plan. However, it was found that rag pickers collect reusable material at various levels, which accounts for Rs 900 million every year.

Figure. 2 : Solid waste landfill site in village Keru

Figure 3 : Characteristics of Jodhpur municipal solid waste (Source : JMC)

4. The evolution of landfill technologies through out history

Until recently, the practice concerning land filling was employed to deposit solid waste for disposal. Consequently, little attention was given to their construction. Depositing the garbage in the Earth’s upper crust was seen as the most secure method of waste disposal. However, because to the fast process of industrialization and urbanization, the

Figure-4 : Flow chart of SWM facilities

practice of land filling has undergone significant changes. Due of the potential pollution caused by unregulated landfills and the occurrence of accidents, rules have been implemented to govern the placement, design, preparation, and management of

Table-3 : Chemical Composition of waste sample From Keru Landfill

PARAMETERS	UNIT	TEST METHOD	RESULT
pH(1:2.5 suspension)		IS 2720 : 1987 (Reaffirmed Year : 2021)-Part 26	7.71
Electrical Conductivity at 25° C (1:2 suspension)	mS/cm	IS 14767:2000 (Reaffirmed Year : 2021)	2400
Moisture Content	%	IS 2720 : 1992 (Reaffirmed Year : 2021)-Part 9	50.60
Ash Content	%	Muffle Furnace	91.22
Carbon as C	%	-	0.81
Hydrogen as H ₂	%	-	0.27
Nitrogen as N	%	-	0.08
Sodium, Na	mg/kg	USDA, NRCS 6P1a	720
Potassium, K	mg/kg	USDA, NRCS 6Q1a	40
Calcium, Ca ⁺²	mg/kg	USDA, NRCS 6N1a	424
Phosphorus, P	mg/kg	USDA, NRCS 4DS	0.05
Iron, Fe	mg/kg	USDA, NRCS 6C	435.8
Cadmium, Cd	mg/kg	USDA, NRCS 8N1	6.8
Chromium, Cr	mg/kg	USDA, NRCS 8Q1a	90.6
Cobalt, Co	mg/kg	USDA, NRCS 8R1a	110
Copper, Cu	mg/kg	USDA, NRCS 8L1a	102.3
Zinc, Zn	mg/kg	USDA, NRCS 8M1a	160.4
Manganese, Mn	mg/kg	USDA, NRCS 6N1a	1.3
Nickel, Ni	mg/kg	USDA, NRCS 6N1a	1.2
Lead, Pb	mg/kg	USDA, NRCS 6N1a	74.3
Organic Carbon	%	IS 2720 : 1972 (Reaffirmed Year : 2020) PART 22	0.95
Organic Matter	%	IS 2720 : 1972 (Reaffirmed Year : 2020) PART 22	1.63
C/N Ratio	-	-	11:1

landfills. Landfills were required to have a specific level of engineering. Figure 3 depicts the schematic portrayal of landfills. The selection of landfill locations is determined by several criteria, and the process requires the completion of an Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA). Important factors to

consider while selecting a landfill site are the availability of land for extended dumping periods and the availability of cover material.

As a result of these technical interventions, landfills have been made more secure, resulting in improved conditions

inside the designated areas for waste decomposition. By effectively sealing cells with a daily cover, the occurrence of public annoyance may be minimized, while also enhancing anaerobic conditions inside the cell and shortening the lifespan of the landfill. This would result in heightened release of landfill gas (LFG) and its subsequent dispersion into the atmosphere poses a possible hazard to the Earth's ecosystem, contributing to global warming. However, LFG has significant energy potential, which is contingent upon the waste composition and other factors. Usually, the landfill gas (LFG) that is gathered is used for the purpose of generating power and providing boiler heating in different businesses.

Figure 5 : Schematic representation of a landfill

4.1 USA Experiences

It has been shown that LFG may be used for power production via the use of both single and dual fuel engines. It may serve as a fuel for cooking and heating boilers in

different treatment systems. The efficient use of landfill gas (LFG) in countries like the USA and Europe not only offers a remedy for waste management and yet additionally makes a substantial contribution to the creation of non-renewable energy and the reduction of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from municipal solid waste (MSW). In 1997, LFG provided a significant amount of power in the USA, reaching $952,314 \times 10^3$ kWh ($3.428E+9$ MJ). This makes LFG the second largest contributor to the renewable energy sector, behind the hydroelectric industry (DOE/EIA, 1999). Between 1993 and 1997, the industrial sector in the USA utilized a considerable portion of biomass energy, namely municipal solid waste (MSW) and landfill gas (LFG), amounting to 73% of the total consumption (DOE/EIA, 1999). In 1997, there were 133 landfill sites in the USA that were actively extracting landfill gas (LFG), with around 120 of them using this gas to generate electricity for power plants. The total generating capacity of these plants is 832 MW.

The majority of landfills in the United States are built only for trash disposal, without any consideration for methane production and collection in their designs. Consequently, the rate at which gas is produced is reduced since the landfill design process does not take into account any measures to increase gas output.

4.2 The Indian Landfill Scenario

The Indian situation regarding landfill technology is examined in this section.

Despite India's tropical climate and its potential as an ideal location for implementing a landfill system for waste disposal with gas recovery, no initiatives are

currently being undertaken to construct it. The high proportion of decomposable organic matter and the higher moisture content in Indian municipal solid waste (MSW) significantly promotes gas production, as stated by Bhide (1994). The municipal solid waste (MSW) in Jodhpur is composed of around 40% organic along with decomposable materials, with a moisture level exceeding 50%. However, despite all of this, municipal solid waste (MSW) in India is still being discarded in open landfills. Because of the high organic waste content and moisture levels in MSW in India, along with the tropical environment, LFG is produced even at open dumps and released into the atmosphere. Furthermore, inappropriate dumping results in the use of a larger amount of space. In densely populated urban areas like Jodhpur, when the current dumpsites become full, waste is redirected to abandoned lands that are unsuitable for the disposal of waste and the generation of landfill gas (LFG). The release of LFG into the atmosphere from these open dumps is a significant concern for climate change experts. Therefore, in order to mitigate this hazard, the Government of India has lately mandated the use of appropriately engineered landfills for the disposal of municipal solid waste (MSW).

Considering the recently established regulations for well-designed landfills, the municipal solid waste (MSW) from Jodhpur, which contains a significant amount of organic matter and moisture, would lead to increased gas production. This gas production also requires adequate management. In addition, because methane is a significant component of LFG and has substantial energy content, it is necessary to assess its energy potential. This has the potential to pave the path for the collection of

LFG (landfill gas) and its utilization for diverse applications.

4.3 Landfill gas emissions

During the decomposition process in landfills, trash generates biogas consisting of roughly 45% carbon dioxide (CO₂) and 55% methane (CH₄) (Bhide, 1994; EIIP, 1999). This gas is referred to as LFG, which stands for Landfill Gas. Because methane is present, LFG possesses a heat content of around 500 BTU/ft³ (18629.5 KJ/m³), which is almost half the heat content of commercially available natural gas.

In order to achieve the requirements of generating gas for energy, reducing GHG emissions, and accommodating the large amount of area needed for traditional landfills, it is necessary to enhance the design along with layout of landfills. The suggested design might potentially be enhanced for economic efficiency.

5. Proposed approach for the redesigned

Considering the inadequate state of waste management along with landfills, along with the lack of private involvement in current landfills, a novel approach to landfill design has been devised. This approach aims to incentivize private engagement in waste management through economic benefits. The suggested design relies on a comprehensive strategy for waste management and power production. This strategy is only applicable to the suggested new landfills. It cannot be implemented on the current landfills.

The following premises are assumed:

- Waste is sorted at its origin and should have a minimal amount of recyclable material when it arrives at the landfill.

- In many cases, it is preferable to directly transport waste to landfills with modified designs located in various parts of the mainland. This allows for lower transportation costs and more effective waste collection. In this revised design technique, as opposed to the traditional approach, the land need is calculated based on the amount of garbage generated and the lifespan of the landfill. The number of cells needed is then computed accordingly.

1. Calculate Waste Generation Rates (WGR):

- Waste Generation Rate (WGR) in 2024:

$$\text{WGR}_{2024} = 700\text{tpd} / 1625,000 \text{ people} = 0.000431 \text{ tpd/person}$$

- Waste Generation Rate (WGR) in 2034:

$$\text{WGR}_{2034} = 1000\text{tpd} / 2,058,000 \text{ people} = 0.000486 \text{ tpd/person}$$

2. Estimate Total Waste Generation:

- Total Waste Generated Annually in 2024:

$$\text{Total Waste}_{2024} = \text{WGR}_{2024} * \text{Population in 2024} * 365 \text{ days/year}$$

$$\text{Total Waste}_{2024} = 0.000431 \text{ tpd/person} * 1,625,000 * 365 = 267,126 \text{ tons/year}$$

- Total Waste Generated Annually in 2034:

$$\text{Total Waste}_{2034} = \text{WGR}_{2034} * \text{Population in 2034} * 365 \text{ days/year}$$

$$\text{Total Waste}_{2034} = 0.000486 \text{ tpd/person} * 2,058,000 * 365 = 360,216 \text{ tons/year}$$

3. Determine Landfill Capacity:

1. Assuming a 20-year operational period (2024 to 2044), calculate the total waste to be disposed of:

$$\text{Total Waste Volume} = (\text{Total Waste}_{2024} + \text{Total Waste}_{2034}) * 20 \text{ years}$$

$$\text{Total Waste Volume} = (360,216 \text{ tons/year} + 267,126 \text{ tons/year}) * 20 \text{ years} = 12,545,840 \text{ tons}$$

$$\text{Compacted specific waste of solid in landfill} = 1100 \text{ kg/m}^3$$

$$\text{Average height of compacted solid waste in landfill} = 8 \text{ m}$$

Considering 30% waste to be fed to landfill.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Area required for one decade} &= (30 \% \text{ of } 700 \text{ tons} / 1100 \text{ kg/m}^3 / 8 \text{ m} * 365 \text{ days} * 10 \text{ years}) \\ &+ (30\% \text{ of } 1000 \text{ tons} / 1100 \text{ kg/m}^3 / 8 \text{ m} * 365 \text{ days} * 10 \text{ years}) = 8.71 \text{ hac.} + 12.45 \text{ hac.} = 21.16 \text{ hac.} \end{aligned}$$

$$15\% \text{ of dumping area} = 21.16 * 0.15 = 3.17 \text{ hac.}$$

$$\text{Total land fill area} = \text{total dump area} + 15\% \text{ of dump area} = 21.2 + 3.2 = 24.4 \text{ hac. (500m} * 488 \text{ m).}$$

Cell Area

The landfill area is specifically built to be operational for the duration of 20 years until it is closed. Hence, the landfill is partitioned into four cells, with each cell covering an area of 5.6 hectares and undergoing its closure at a time duration of 3 years. The total number of cells is 4. The area of each cell is 5.6 square meters, with dimensions of 200 meters * 280 meters. The duration of closure for each phase is 5 years.

An analysis of the Jodhpur Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) will be conducted.

The viability of PBLF as an alternative energy source is being evaluated by applying it in a case study with municipal solid waste (MSW) in Jodhpur city. The typical attributes of The Jodhpur Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) regulations are provided in Section 2. The model parameter details for this case study are provided below:

The total amount of garbage created is 750 tons each day, which is equivalent to 2,73,750 tons per year.

The total amount of rubbish collected is 2,73,750 tons, with a collection efficiency of 100%.

The planned method aims to landfill 35% of the garbage.

The fraction of assimilable organic carbon in land-filled trash is 0.6, according to the EIIP (1999) and Johennessen (1999).

The rate of LFG generation is 720 cubic meters per hour.

The methane concentration in landfill gas (LFG) is 0.55, assuming typical temperature and pressure conditions.

The gas collecting efficiency is 80%.

The calorific value of methane is 9000 Kcal/m³, which is the lowest number.

The statistics shown above have been obtained from many experimental experiments documented in the literature (Bhide, 1994; IIT, 1997; LMOP-EPA, 1996; Peavy and Rowe, 1989; Yedla and Parikh, 2001). The gas collecting efficiency has been adopted from the US landfill system due to the absence of any relevant expertise specific to Indian circumstances.

The energy potential, measured in kilocalories (Kcal), has been determined using the following calculation:

$$Er = 273750 \times 0.35 \times 0.6 \times 720 \times 0.55 \times 0.8 \times 9000$$

The Jodhpur Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) has the potential to produce a net methane energy of 163.90 billion Kcal annually. The LFG created has a coal equivalence of 0.92, a density of 0.722×10^3 t/m³, and a calorific value of 9000 Kcal/m³. The total coal equivalence of the LFG generated is 0.145 million tons. At a price of Rs. 800 per ton, the PBLF system has the potential to generate methane worth Rs. 219.0 million per year (equivalent to US\$1.825 million per year).

The excavated compost has the potential to be used in agriculture, however it must undergo pilot-scale testing. Enhancing the worth of the extracted manure will greatly enhance the cost-effectiveness of this procedure.

Due to the presence of certain crucial assumptions in the proposed system, it is necessary to conduct barrier analysis and adaptation tests. The cost-benefit analysis conducted by Yedla and Parikh (2001) used inflation-adjusted data from the USEPA to estimate the expenses associated with landfill preparation and maintenance. Another analysis demonstrated that the financial viability of the newly suggested system remains unaffected by the addition of landfill preparation expenses and maintenance. This technique is comprehensive and combines many issue areas to get a distinct conclusion. Additional research is planned to assess its applicability, first on a small scale along with then on a large one.

6. Conclusions

The landfill situation has been evolving over time. Due to the rising rates of trash creation, limited land availability, and concerns about global warming, it is crucial to make adjustments to current landfill designs that focus on generating energy from garbage and demand less space. A revised design was suggested taking into account both theoretical issues and the quantities of waste creation. A case study revealed the potential to produce energy valued at Rs. 219.0 million by harnessing landfill gas, which is comparable to 0.145 million tons of coal. The new approach has made it possible to save land by using cells that only require a fixed area of land. In contrast, conventional designs would require land continuously because it takes more than 20 years for the

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waste to fully compost and settle in landfills designed according to existing procedures. Therefore, the LFSGR, based on the recently suggested landfill design, will provide superior performance in terms of land conservation and energy production.

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Assessing human perception towards Electric Vehicle (EV) – A Case Study for Kolkata, West Bengal, India

I. Mukherjee

Associate Professor, Civil Engineering Department, Aliah University, Kolkata, Email-drindranilmukherjee.ce@aliah.ac.in

K. Ghosh

Associate Professor, Department of Basic Science & Humanities, Techno International New Town, Kolkata, Email-kakali.ghosh@tict.edu.in

M. Dey

Associate Professor, Department of MBA, IMS Business School, Kolkata, Email- moumi.mail@gmail.com

Md. W. Akram

Assistant Professor, Civil Engineering Department, Aliah University, Kolkata, Email- wasim.ce@aliah.ac.in

R. Paul

Technical Assistant, Civil Engineering Department, Aliah University, Kolkata, Email- reshmipaul@aliah.ac.in

Abstract:

Over the last decade the automobile sector has witnessed a marked change as far as research in the sector is concerned. With increased pollutant emissions recorded worldwide and having direct correlation with the conventional fuel used for the automobiles, the research in the field has mostly concentrated on the use of alternative fuel and thereby to reduce the emissions. But at the same time its quite pertinent to understand and assess the perception of the end user stemming across various ages and also from different classes of the society. The present study tries to report on this for the metropolis Kolkata which happens to be one of the most polluted cities in India and also has high traffic density.

***Corresponding author:** *wasim.ce@aliah.ac.in*

Regression analysis using ANOVA has been used to ascertain the correlation of the human perceptions analyzed through a questionnaire with the corresponding trend in EV use and its tangible and intangible environmental benefits.

Keywords: *EV, Human Perception, Cleaner Environment, Fossil Fuel, Regression Analysis*

Introduction:

Industrial growth coupled with rapid urbanization and dependency of individuals towards advanced technology happens to be the order of the day. In this context, there has been immense development in the automobile sector. On one hand the dependency on fossil fuel marked with its detrimental impact on the surrounding environment looming large and on the other hand, the hand shaking towards new technology in the form Electric Vehicles (EVs) is creating a change in perception towards these two options amongst the buyers. There is not an iota of doubt that the shift to EVs indicates a drastic reduction in the atmospheric pollutant levels including the corresponding lowering of some of the indirect GHG emissions (CO, SO₂, NO_x). From the life cycle emissions analysis it has been established that as compared to internal combustion engine vehicles which are mostly in vogue, EVs provide upto 50% lowering of green house emissions and upto 80% lower local air emission. The focus has also been on power trains with EV mode for reduced fossil fuel dependency and thus lowered atmospheric pollution. As a result, majority of countries' Governments are now in the formulation of policies such as code and adoption strategies for EV. However, strangely as reported for the year 2019 the market share of electric vehicles has been found to be low and it only amounts to 2%. This finding places the manufacturers of the

passenger vehicles under analysis at a 6% market share of total sales. It is evident that perceptions and use by the consumer play a central role in how the innovation is adopted and accepted in the case of an EV. According to certain research carried out with regards to the acceptance of EVs, consumers were taken back by the price of the car, range of the vehicle, availability of the charging stations and battery life and performance. On the same note, environmental factors as well as pull factor for new technology play a role in the customers' lust for EVs in some segments. Thus, the consumer perceptions have to be examined and how these perceptions vary by the population demographic and influence purchase of electric vehicles. In light of these, this research aims at determining the perception of consumers in the India market on electric vehicles, their attitude and their intention to use electric vehicles in the future. Employing a different methodology from the literature review, the study proceeds to incorporate age, income, and location of the respondents across the Indian territory by administering a structured and validated survey instrument in addition to closed-ended questions on the factors influencing perception and willingness to adopt EVs. The technique of Hypothesis testing is also used with special reference to differences in the response amongst the subgroups of the total respondents. Also, to obtain the acceptance estimates, the respondents are also asked about their perception about the improvement of EV in the next ten years.

(Ghasri et al,2019) conducted a study in New South Wales, Australia to understand the inclination of the people towards EVs. The study was conducted by a survey and the target audience was three generations. The

study confirmed the varied perception of the community towards adoption of EVs based on incentives offered for the initial price compared to ongoing incentives for operating costs. It was also reported that the financial incentives offered to the consumers as a rebate on the purchase price lures them more to purchase the EVs rather than offering the same incentive to manufacturers to reduce the purchase price. In another study conducted by (Liao et al, 2016)it was observed that the various influential factors which determine the consumer preferences towards adoption of EVs are mostly the socio-economic variables, psychological factors, mobility condition, social influence, etc. The study also reported on formulating a research plan for enhancing the acceptability of EVs by the consumers for a cleaner environment. In another study conducted by (Muthukrishnan et al, 2023), survey was conducted amongst about 170 respondents, selected through favorable sampling methods and data was collected through a questionnaire monitored via Google Forms, which had close-ended questions and Likert scale questions. The findings of the study reported on the positive perception of the respondents towards EVs. The two ruling factors identified was the cheap operating cost of the Evs and its eco-friendly nature. The main factor regarding non acceptability of the EVs was identified as the dearth of proper knowledge towards the Evs. (Pattisapu et al, 2022) conducted a study to understand the inclination of consumers towards EVs using national level data and also by considering different classes of cities deploying machine learning method and relative weight analysis. The study reported on the current service-related infrastructural conditions, operation-maintenance-capital cost as the major

hindrances towards the adoption of EVs by the consumers.

(Alia, et al 2022) conducted a study thrusting the adoption of EVs by the people as a boon to save the surrounding environment by reducing atmospheric emissions as well as promoting clean and green energy. The study also tried to understand the various factors influencing the willingness of the consumers towards EVs and also the expectations of the consumers from EVs. The present paper tries to throw light on the perception of the EVs for the city of Kolkata, West Bengal, India. The study is important from the context of increased atmospheric pollution which the city is experiencing over the last decade (www.wbpcb.gov.in) and also reflected in the high Air Quality Index for the metropolis. With the projected EVs market share of 30% in PVs by 2030, the study becomes more so important to address the perceptions for highly congested and polluted cities like the one Kolkata in the present study. The study also offers a comparative reduction in the atmospheric pollutants due to the adoption of EVs and also lowering the dependency on fossil fuel.

Study Area:

Kolkata (22.572645°N, 88.363892°E), West Bengal, India was taken as the study area. The metropolis nearly covers an area of 185 km² with an elevation of 9.14 m and a population of 1.49 crores as recorded for the year 2020. The city has a wide varied population type in terms of culture, religion, age and occupancy level. In fact, these variations are very intrinsic to the carrying out of a survey for unbiased results. The perception parameter is very much individual centric and hence it is best analysed for diversified population. The study tried to float the questionnaire to this

diversified population for obtaining feedback on the adoption of EV by the mass.

Methodology:

Methodology Outline for Study on EV Perception and Adoption in Kolkata

1. Research Design:

- **Objective:** Thus, the study aims at evaluating the general attitude of the people towards the use of EVs and the association between the attitude and the level of adoption and interest of the people in the EVs and their impact on the environment in Kolkata.

2. Sampling Frame:

Population: People of all age groups and from different economic classes residing in Kolkata.

Sampling Method: People living in Kolkata belong to all age groups and different classes of society.

Age Groups: Samples are: young adults; middle-aged persons; and seniors.

Socioeconomic Classes: Based on income or socio-economic status

3. Data Collection:

To create a close ended questionnaire using a Likert scale on a Google form, focusing on the following topics.:

Demographic information: sex, age, income level, education level, etc.

Perceptions on EVs: about the technology of EVs, perceived benefits on the environment, economic advantages with EVs, concerns such as cost, range, charging infrastructure for EVs, as well as willingness to own and/or purchase EVs.

Environmental Awareness: Sentimentally utilizing environmental issues such as pollution, climate change, and the perceptions of consumers about EVs as a solution.

4. Data Analysis:

● **Quantitative Analysis:**

Descriptive Statistics: In giving the demographic characteristics and the other key variables, one has to give a brief summary of them.

Regression Analysis: Find out the relationships between perceptions (DP) and trends or concerns about adoption (EA (IV)).

Types of Regression: Perception analysis through multiple regression to determine the extent of the effect of different variables on the topic under consideration.

● **Qualitative Analysis:**

Thematic Analysis: All the informal answers should be analyzed in terms of typical issues that concern the adoption of electric vehicles (EVs) and their preferences.

5. Limitations:

- **Geographical Focus:** carried out among the pupils in Kolkata only, and therefore the findings may not be generalized to other parts of the country.
- **Response bias:** possible subjectivity of the data and selection of a sample.
- **Temporal Constraints:** One of the main drawbacks of using the current perceptions as the basis of WHO's analyses is the inability to track the changes in perceptions over time in real-time.

6. Implications and Recommendations:

- **Policy Implications:** Provide policymakers with information regarding people's attitudes towards EVs and awareness of environmental issues.
- **Industry Implications:** Counsel automotive manufacturers and other players in the industry on how best they can popularize EV technology.
- **Future Research Directions:** Enumerate recommendations for other research with reference to the study outcomes.

This methodology outlines a systematic approach to investigating the perspectives of Kolkata residents regarding the adoption of electric vehicles and their environmental concerns. By employing advanced statistical analysis, thorough data gathering methods, and careful sampling, the research aims to clarify the factors affecting the transition from gasoline-powered automobiles to electric vehicles in metropolitan settings.

Results and Discussion:

The study centered around the feedbacks obtained from the questionnaire circulated amongst the mass in the vicinity of 100 belonging to different age groups and areas in Kolkata, and was analysed with respect to three principal parameters Age group, Fuel cost incurred (Rs) per month and Distance driven in miles per week towards the attitude of the mass towards adoption of EVs (Positive Response Percentage). The data has been reported in Tables 1, 2 and 3 respectively. In order to understand the trend in the inclination of the mass towards EVs, a simple linear regression analysis was performed and the results of it have been shown in Fig 1, 2 and 3 respectively.

Table 1

Age group	Positive Response Percentage
18-24	72
25-34	53
35-44	45
45-54	61
55-65	100

Table 2

Fuel Cost Incurred (Rs) per month	Positive Response Percentage
0-2000	71
2000-5000	37.5
5000-10000	57
10000-15000	54

Table 3

Distance (miles)/week	Positive Percentage Response
0-50	56
51-100	59
101-200	57
201-300	50
>300	50

Figure 1: Positive Response Percentage vs Age Group

From Figure 1, the perception towards the adoption of EVs in the age group of (25-44) shows a downward trend from the age group (18-24) but a gradual increase after that in the age group of 44 plus. Although a value of 100% positive

response have been observed for the higher age group (>65), but the number of respondents reported for this group is not appreciably high enough to confirm the value. This can be attributed to the gradual inclination of the more matured masses towards using EVs for a greener and cleaner environment. The R^2 value obtained also is significantly low (0.2242) which possibly suggests towards the possible scatteredness in the data set and the varied perception of the mass towards the adoption of EVs. From Figure 2 it is observed that masses who practically have no vehicles or spend in the lower range of Rs (0-2000) are more cautious about the environment and are more inclined towards the adoption of EVs. This is not reflected in the affluent classes from the dataset observed. However, here also the R^2 value obtained is

Figure 2 : Positive Response Percentage vs Fuel Cost Incurred in INR per Month

Figure 3: Positive Response Percentage vs Distance driven in miles per week

appreciably low (0.0875)) suggesting the variation in the dataset encountered. From Figure 3, the R^2 value obtained is quite high (0.6373) suggesting the closeness in the dataset. Also the positive response percentage has been observed to be significantly high for the masses travelling in the (51-200) miles per week, signifying the awareness of mostly the daily commuters towards a greener environment by showing positive inclination towards the adoption of EVs.

Conclusion:

There is no doubt that the present generation and the generations to come do deserve a greener and cleaner environment to survive and sustain in the future. The global pollution levels are indeed staggering and are sending alarms every day. In this context, as vehicular emissions happen to be one of the significant contributors to global pollutions, hence to curb it, EVs are one of the solutions. The present study has made an attempt to report and analyse the perception towards the adoption of EVs for masses in Kolkata, West Bengal, India. The dataset have shown a moderate inclination with the major criteria as per the analysis being done, being found to be the steady inclination driven towards adoption of EVs with respect to the distance driven in miles per week (> 50%). Also significant positive response percentage (70%) has been observed for those who spend less for fuel cost every month which suggests the awareness of the EVs more among the lesser affluent sections of the society and everywhere as middle class happens to be the backbone of any progress, this is indeed a good sign.

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AN APPEAL

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Improved Two-Way Surge Tank for Water Hammer Control on Low and Medium Head Pumping Mains

N. R. Paunikar

*Research Scholar, Civil Engineering Department, Government College of Engineering, Amravati-444604, Maharashtra, India
Email: nrpaunikar@yahoo.co.in*

R. K. Rai

*Associate Professor, Civil Engineering Department, Government College of Engineering, Yavatmal-445001, Maharashtra, India
Email: rairampravesh@yahoo.co.in*

Abstract:

Two-way surge tank is a low cost, maintenance-free and control-free water hammer control device. This device is an improved version of one-way surge tank by overcoming its demerits and incorporating features to make it suitable for controlling both down surge and upsurge. The device can be installed at the pumping station and/or enroute location. The condition for suitability is that the water hammer head should be higher than the steady state head at location of installation which can be satisfied in and is, thus, suitable for low and medium head pumping mains. The concept of and basis for quantity discharged from two-way surge tanks are well reported in literature, discussed in this paper, and further improvements proposed to enhance effectiveness, reliability, and safe margin for capacity of the device. The paper also discusses optimisation of capacity and installation level of the tank. Two-way surge tanks are installed in some schemes and performances at all the installations over period 5-30 years are observed unfailling and fully satisfactory.

Key Words : *Down surge, one-way surge tank, surge tank, two-way surge tank, upsurge, water column separation.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Two-way surge tank is modified version of one-way surge tank as water hammer control (WHC) device by incorporating improvements to overcome its demerits. One-way surge tank is also improved version of conventional surge tank by restricting height of tank to normal construction limit. These three devices function on a principle to supply stored water to the pipeline subjected to transient low pressures to fill low pressure zone, prevent water column separation, and decelerate rate of change of flow velocity in the pipeline, thereby reduce the down surge. Brief features, similarities, and differences of these three devices are as follows:

Top of the surge tank is, essentially kept above hydraulic grade level (HGL) to avoid overflow from the tank during normal operation. Constraint for the device is feasibility of construction of the tank to required height corresponding to HGL above ground level (GL). Normal limit is 20 to 25 m. Despite superior merits, the device is rarely selected as HGL at the installation is usually higher than the limit.

One-way surge tank overcomes this problem by keeping top of the tank below HGL and providing a non-return valve (NRV) in connecting pipe to disallow inflow to the tank (Figure 1).

A short connecting pipe is provided from bottom of the tank to pipeline along with NRV installed with direction to allow flow from the tank to the pipeline. Under normal operation, the NRV is held closed due to higher pressure on downstream face as per HGL at tee-junction against lower pressure on upstream face as per water level (WL) in the tank. A small feed line is provided from the connecting pipe to the tank with a float valve at the top to close, or alternatively an

Figure 1: One-Way Surge Tank

altitude valve in feed line to stop flow when WL reaches top water level. On power failure to the pumps, when the pressure at the tee-junction falls below WL in the tank due to down surge, water from the tank flows through connecting pipe and NRV into the pipeline and restrict magnitude of down surge.

Limitation of the device is that it can effectively function only if the minimum pressure at the junction during down surge falls below WL in the tank. As elevation of WL above GL is of small magnitude compared to steady state head (H_0), it can be stated that H_0 should be significantly lower than the water hammer head. Hence, condition for suitability shall be mathematically as:

$$H_0 \ll \left(\frac{c V_0}{g} \right) \quad (1)$$

Where, c = speed of transient pressure wave, V_0 = steady state velocity, g = acceleration due to gravity, and cV_0/g = water hammer head. This condition can be satisfied in low and medium head systems only, but, not in high head systems. Therefore, one-way surge

tank, and similarly, two-way surge tanks are suitable for low and medium head pumping systems.

Two important demerits of one-way surge tank are as follows:

- (i) Float valve starts leaking after a few years of operation. Pumped water is wasted along with energy consumed to pump the wasted water. As an alternative to float valve, altitude valve can be selected. However, reliability of the altitude valve is doubtful; and,
- (ii) The one-way surge tank has no capability to control upsurge.

Due to these demerits, one-way surge tank is not preferred device. Two-way surge tank is improved version of one-way surge tank and addresses the demerits.

2. CONCEPT OF TWO-WAY SURGE TANK

Bosserman II (2008) discussed the concept of Two-Way Surge Tank illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Conceptual Two-Way Surge Tank [Source; Bosserman II (2008)]

A closed vessel or tank in steel construction is provided as two-way surge tank as against open to atmosphere one-way surge tank. Necessity of the float valve or altitude valve is, thus eliminated. A combination of vacuum breaker and air release valve is installed on the top of the tank.

Functioning of two-way surge tank is as follows:

Under steady state condition, the two-way surge tank is completely filled with water under pressure as per HGL. When transient surge gradient falls below the tank, outflow from the tank commences, and passes into the pumping main filling low pressure zone, and, thereby reducing the down surge. Due outflow, the pressure in the tank falls. When the pressure falls below atmospheric pressure, the vacuum breaker activates and admits air into the tank and prevents vacuum. On flow reversal, water from pipeline flows into the tank pressurizing both water and air. The air release valve slowly expels the air and the tank is refilled with water.

3. DRAWBACKS IN CONCEPTUAL ARRANGEMENT AND IMPROVEMENTS

3.1 Vacuum Breaker Valve

Vacuum breaker valve is not reliable to admit air as it incorporates linkages which are prone to failure. If vacuum breaker fails to function, two-way surge tank will drain partly until internal pressure falls to vapour pressure i.e., about -9.5 m. At this pressure, part of water vaporises resulting in formation of vapour pocket, disallowing further drop in pressures and stopping outflow from the tank. Thus, the two-way surge tank becomes non-functional and protection is lost.

Martin (2008) illustrates alternative vacuum breaker arrangement incorporating NRV as vacuum breaker installed near top of the tank shown in Figure 3. The direction of NRV shall be to open towards tank to admit air from the atmosphere. This arrangement is tried in many two-way surge tanks over 30 years and found unfailling.

3.2 Reduction in Upsurge

Conceptual arrangement does not incorporate any feature to reduce the upsurge. If arrangement for throttling reverse flow is incorporated, magnitude of the upsurge can be reduced due to head loss incurred in throttling arrangement.

Figure 3: Vacuum Breaking Arrangement (with NRV)

Thorley (2004) illustrated the arrangement for an air vessel by incorporating NRV in connecting pipe to disallow reverse flow and by providing small diameter bypass to NRV which throttles reverse flow. This throttling feature is adopted in some air vessels to control pressure rise as an alternative to differential throttling orifices. The arrangement is, thus, proven, and can be adopted for the two-way surge tank (Figure 4).

3.3 Air Valve

On flow reversal, the flow pressurises the air in the tank. If air release is very slow, higher pressure shall be built up. If air release is rapid, it can damage ball of air valve. Hence, air release should be at moderate rate for which kinetic double orifice air valves are proposed and discussed in Section 6.

Figure 4: Modified Two Way Surge Tank (with NRV as Vacuum Breaker & Bypass Piping)

3.4 Merits of modified Two-Way Surge Tank

Merits of the device are as follows:

- (i) Elevation of tank above GL can be kept within feasible limit of construction;
- (ii) Being a closed vessel, no possibility of overflow and no wastage of pumped water and energy;
- (iii) Two-way surge tank does not include any moving or rotating component or control feature. The device is, thus, maintenance-free, and, control-free; and,
- (iv) Due to incorporation of bypass, the reverse flow can be throttled to reduce upsurge.

4. QUANTITY DISCHARGED FROM TWO-WAY SURGE TANK

Stephenson (1989) has derived equation for determining quantity discharged by one-way surge tank to the pipeline. Since, during the down surge, two-way surge tank functions in similar manner to supply flow to the pipeline, the equation can also be applied for the device. The approach for deriving equation is based on calculating the distance travelled by liquid column in coming to rest i.e., volume of cavity in the pipeline, and thus, quantity discharged (Qty) from one-way/ two-way surge tank to fill the cavity. The equation is:

$$Qty = \frac{A_p L V_0^2}{2 g h} \quad (2)$$

Where, A_p = cross sectional area of pipeline; L = length of pipeline from the tank to discharging reservoir or next tank; g = acceleration due to gravity; and, h =static head above the two-waysurge tank to reservoir or next tank.

It can be seen from the Equation (2) that quantity discharged is inversely proportional

to 'h'. Thus, if 'h' is kept smaller, quantity discharged increases and vice versa. This inference can be applied for optimization of elevation of tank.

5. DESIGN ASPECTS OF TWO-WAY SURGE TANK

5.1 Capacity of Tank

A margin of 75-100% for small tank, 50-75% for medium tank and 25-50% for large tank is desirable for design capacity above quantity discharged to meet following operational aspects:

- (i) Increase in discharge due to higher WL in intake, or lower friction in pipeline, or higher frequency of power supply;
- (ii) Some water column above lip of outlet of tank is necessary to prevent ingress of air at entrance to outlet pipe;
- (iii) Probability of subsequent power failure before the tank is refilled.

5.2 Design of Tank

The tank may be vertical or horizontal depending on capacity and dimensions and a single or multiple tanks if capacity is large. Dished ends on both sides and 450-500 mm diameter manhole on the top of tank shall be provided. The tank shall be fabricated from mild steel plates. Shell thickness and thickness of dished ends shall be based on formulae and charts given in IS 2825-1969: Code for unfired pressure vessels. Corrosion allowance shall be considered. Design pressure shall be equal to sum of maximum operating pressure and uncontrolled water hammer head even if protection device is provided. Underlying basis for higher design pressure is that even if the device becomes non-functional for any reason, the tank should be suitable to withstand the

maximum pressure encountered including uncontrolled water hammer pressure. This approach is also based on consideration that burst in the tank with pressurised air inside is very dangerous.

5.3 Appurtenances on the Tank and Pipeline

Following valves and fittings are necessary (Figure 4):

- (i) Two numbers of NRV as vacuum breakers below the top of the tank along with isolating valve, piping, and bend;
- (ii) Adequate number of kinetic double orifice/combination air valves with isolation valves on top of the tank (Minimum two numbers, and more air valves if longer tank is longer);
- (iii) Drain valve at bottom with drain pipe;
- (iv) Outlet-cum connecting pipe with NRV and isolating valve;
- (v) A bypass piping to NRV; and,
- (vi) A safety valve on top of the tank;

If multiple tanks are provided, a manifold arrangement shall be provided to which connecting pipe from each tank shall be jointed with a provision for isolating any connecting pipe. In addition, 32/40 diameter air piping connected to each tank with isolating valve shall be provided.

6. SIZING OF IMPORTANT COMPONENTS

Important components are, namely, outlet-cum connecting pipe, by-pass to NRV, air valves and NRV-type vacuum breaker.

6.1 Outlet-cum Connecting Pipe

Criteria for sizing the piping should be that head loss in the outlet-cum connecting

pipe and NRV in the pipe should be as low as possible to maximize outflow from the tank in order to minimize down surge. Maximum rate of outflow occurs immediately after power failure to the pumps and thus, shall be design value. This piping comprises four elements i.e. entrance bell mouth to the outlet piping, connecting pipe, NRV and exit at tee-junction. Criteria for sizing piping recommended by noted investigators and authors of books on water hammer are;

- (i) The diameter of the outlet from the one-way surge tank shall be nearly the same diameter of the main pipeline [Thorley 2004];
- (ii) Normal velocity through the connecting pipe can be in the range of 3 to 5 m/s and if maximum velocity exceeds 5 m/s, such high velocity can be tolerated if the same is for a very short duration (about 1s). The size should be based on cost consideration along with maximum velocity through the pipe. [Sridharan 2005]

Wide variation in opinion of the investigators is seen. Hence, the issue needs to be studied. For evaluating head loss in connecting pipes, three sizes i.e. 0.5 D, 0.75D and 1.0 D (where D = diameter of main pipeline) are considered in the following example:

Main pipeline data: discharge (Q) = 1.5 m³/s, pipeline diameter (D)=1400 mm. The diameters of connecting pipes considered for comparative evaluation are 700 mm (about 0.5 D), 1000 mm (about 0.75 D) and 1400 mm(1.0D). Length of connecting pipe is assumed 25 m and Hazen-Willaims coefficient, $C=130$. Head loss in valves and fittings is given by $H_L=KV_v^2/2g$ where K = coefficient for head loss. Table 1 shows head losses for three sizes of connecting pipe.

**Table 1: Head losses in outlet –cum-connecting pipe
(Typical example: $Q=1.5 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ and $D =1400\text{mm}$)**

Diameter of Connecting Pipe	0.5D (700mm)	0.75D (1000mm)	1.0 D (1400 mm)
Entrance loss at outlet (Bellmouth $K= 0.1$, and $V_o=2.98,1.91,0.85 \text{ m/s}$)	0.05 m	0.024 m	0.004 m
Friction loss in connecting pipe ($C=130,L= 25 \text{ m}$)	0.39m	0.069m	0.013m
Head loss in NRV ($K=2.5$) and butterfly valve ($K=0.4$) ($V_o= 3.9, 1.91, 0.97 \text{ m/s}$)	2.244 m	0.57 m	0.148m
Head loss at tee junction ($K=0.8$)	0.619m	0.149m	0.038 m
Total head loss	3.308m	0.812m	0.203m

It is seen from the above table 1 that head loss is very high if diameter is 0.5D or less. In such a case, outflow from the tank shall be lower and may not be hydraulically effective to restrict the down surge. Head loss in case of 1.0D is very low which shall result in effective outflow from the tank. However, the diameter and cost shall be higher. Connecting pipe of 0.75D is a good compromise between hydraulic effectiveness and cost. The velocity in the pipe shall be below 5.0 m/s which is within abrasion-free limit.

It can, therefore be inferred that connecting a pipe of diameter about 0.75D is preferable.

6.2 Bypass to NRV

Objective of the bypass is to throttle the reverse flow to reduce pressures in the tank. Permissible flow velocity is 10 m/s to avoid abrasive damage to piping [Stephenson

2005]. Maximum recommended velocity in an orifice of the air vessel is 20 m/s [Sridharan 2005].

Considering the opinions of the reputed investigators and the essential requirement that head loss in bypass should be substantial to reduce pressure rise in the tank, three options for diameter of bypass piping for the example in Table 1 are evaluated.

It is seen from the Table 2 that head loss at $V_o= 20 \text{ m/s}$ is very high. Caution needs to be exercised to avoid such very high head loss to prevent pressure reduction to cavitation level. The head loss for $V_o= 10 \text{ m/s}$ is quite low which may not restrict pressure rise effectively. It is, thus can be inferred that bypass shall be sized for flow velocity of approximately 15 m/s. Though the velocity exceeds abrasion-free limit of 10 m/s, the abrasion can be taken care of by providing higher allowance in shell thickness.

Table 2: Head losses in bypass piping in the example ($Q=1.5 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$)

Particulars	$V_o = 10 \text{ m/s}$	$V_o = 15 \text{ m/s}$	$V_o = 20 \text{ m/s}$
Diameter	450 mm	350 mm	300 mm
Actual V_o	9.43 m/s	25.59m/s	21.22 m/s
Head loss in bypass piping ($C=130, L=10 \text{ m}$)	1.34	4.56m	9.68m
Head loss in sluice valve ($K=0.35$)	1.58m	4.33 m	8.03 m
Head loss in 2 numbers of 90p bends ($K = 0.75 \times 2$)	6.78 m	18.58 m	34.42 m
Total head loss	9.7m	27.47m	52.13 m

6.3 Air Valves

Air accumulated in the two-way surge tank during down surge phase need to be expelled completely to make the tank ready for next water hammer event. The air entered in the tank is at atmospheric pressure during down surge and both floats i.e., small orifice and large orifice are in unseated positions. When flow reversal occurs, the flow passes through the bypass of connecting pipe into the tank causing partly compression of air and partly air expulsion to the atmosphere through both orifices. Quantity of air expelled from large orifice is much higher than air flow through small orifice. When pressurised air enters a small orifice chamber, the float shall remain in unseated position till water level rises to orifice at which the uplifted float shuts the orifice. As regards large orifice, the float remains at bottom of air valve chamber and air escapes through the large orifice even with moderate pressure build up. As large quantity of air outflow occurs in the large orifice chamber, the float being lighter (compared to the small orifice float), is likely to get caught in air stream and shut the large orifice prematurely. To prevent such possibility, kinetic air valve needs to be selected.

The expulsion of air needs to be at moderately rapid rate to prevent high pressure rise in the tank. In the example, even if quantity of air admitted is 100 m^3 , the time available for expulsion at the reverse flow rate of $1.5 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ is nearly 66 s. Thus, significantly high air flow rate is necessary for which multiple number of air valves need to be provided.

Based on discussion, the requirement of air valves can be stated as:

- (i) Moderately rapid expulsion of air shall be design and selection basis;
- (ii) The type of air valve should be double orifice air valve comprising both small and large orifices for effectively expelling pressurised air;
- (iii) Kinetic air valve is essential to prevent premature seating of large orifice float;
- (iv) Size of air valve should be higher, preferably 150 mm or 200 mm; and,
- (v) Minimum 2 number of air valves for small tank and higher number for medium and large tanks shall be provided.

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6.4 NRV as Vacuum Breaker

The NRV shall be light weight and swing check type to open rapidly with low resistance to admit air. NRVs of 150-200 mm which fulfils the requirement are preferable. A sluice valve shall be provided on the piping on tank side of the NRV for isolation to attend maintenance. Minimum two number of NRV shall be provided considering maintenance requirement.

7. CONTROLLED WATER HAMMER PRESSURES

Stephenson (1989) illustrates magnitudes for controlled water hammer pressures with one-way surge tank as WHC device depending on value of parameter “ $h/(cV_0/g)$ ”, which is presented in Figure 5. As functioning of the two-way surge tank is

similar, the chart can be considered as applicable for quantity discharged from the two-way surge tank. The chart also gives ratio of quantity of water discharged by the one-way surge tank using elastic water hammer theory to the quantity calculated as per the Equation (2). The conclusions drawn from the Figure 5 are as follows:

- (i) If “ $h/[cV_0/g]$ ” is less than 0.6, i.e., static head (h) on the tank is less than 60% of water hammer head, then h_c (controlled upsurge) in one-way surge tank is within 25% of uncontrolled water hammer head i.e., reduction in water hammer pressure by 75%. Such high reduction generally, results in acceptable safe limit for water hammer protection;
- (ii) If $h/[cV_0/g] = 0.5$ in one-way surge tank, controlled water hammer head is zero. Thus, water hammer is fully nullified if h

Figure 5: Reduced Upsurge with One Way / Two Way Surge Tank [Source: Stephenson (1989)]

is equal to 50% of uncontrolled water hammer head;

- (iii) The points (i) and (ii) regarding upsurge are strictly applicable for the one-way surge tank. As regards, upsurge in case of the two-way surge tank, the reduced down surge shall result in reduced upsurge. However, the pressure rise also depends on compressibility of air under evacuation from the tank. If air outflow rate is equal to water inflow rate, upsurge shall not increase further. Hence, an efficient air outflow is essential to restrict pressure rise in the tank.
- (iv) If ' $h/[cVo/g]$ ' is less than 0.6, quantity discharged from the one-way / two-way surge tank is above 95% of quantity calculated using Equation (2) indicating tolerable error of maximum 5%.
- (v) It is also seen from the Equation (2) that quantity discharged from the tank and therefore, design capacity of tank is lesser if ' h ' is higher. Thus, it can be inferred that the capacity can be optimised if elevation of the tank is kept as near the ground level as possible; and;
- (vi) In addition to above controlled pressures, as effect of throttling in bypass piping, upsurge shall reduce substantially.

8. FIELD INSTALLATION EXPERIENCE

The author¹ has designed and installed 8 number of two-way surge tanks in water supply schemes of various capacities and lengths of pumping mains varying from 1 to 70 km over a period of 30 years in Maharashtra state. In Solapur water supply scheme (WSS), an air vessel was installed at pumping station and two-way surge tank was installed at enroute hump at 25 km

away as multiple water hammer devices for 70 km long pumping main which resulted in substantial reduction in required capacity of the air vessel. Some installations where two-way surge tanks are installed in Maharashtra state are as follows;

- (i) Solapur WSS at enroute hump – 30 years
- (ii) Nagpur WSS (Kanhane source) – 30 years
- (iii) Thane WSS (Pise source Phase 1) - 25 years
- (iv) Thane WSS (Pise source Phase 2) -15 years
- (v) Vasai-Virar WSS (Phase 1) - 30 years
- (vi) Vasai-Virar WSS (Phase 2) - 5 years
- (vii) Temghar clear water pumping system - 25 years
- (viii) Pimpri-Chinchwad WSS – 1 year

In all field installations including enroute tank, the two-way surge tanks are functioning as per design and controlling water hammer pressures, without any failure and need of maintenance. The performance at all installations are thus, fully satisfactory.

Two-way surge tanks are proposed in Surya WSS near Mumbai which is under commissioning and in Ring main system for WSS to Greater Chennai Corporation, but not executed.

9. CONCLUSIONS

Two-way surge tank is answer to demerits of one-way surge tank and conventional surge tank. No movable or rotating components are incorporated making the device maintenance-free and self-regulating. Guidelines to determine capacity, margins with reasonings and criteria for applicability

with parameters, i.e., water hammer head and steady state head are specified. Design aspects of tank, all required piping and appurtenances are discussed and guidelines are specified. Optimisation of the capacity of tank, and elevation is dealt. Controlled upsurge can be determined by selecting the device.

The device is tried at number of schemes for period up to 30years, and the field reports are highly satisfactory. The device is proposed in some prestigious on-going schemes due to high reliability and satisfactory performance.

10. NOTATIONS

A_p = cross-sectional area of pipe

C = Hazen Williams coefficient for friction loss

c = speed of transient pressure wave

D = Diameter of pipeline

g = acceleration due to gravity

h = static head on tank up to reservoir / next tank

h_c = controlled upsurge

H_o = operating head under steady state

L = length of pipeline

K = coefficient for head loss in valve/fitting

Q = Flowrate

Qty = Quantity discharged by one-way/two-way surge tank

V_o = steady state velocity

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Restoration of Ganga River Ecosystem : Issues and Challenges

Dr Arunabha Majumder

Fellow, Institution of Public Health Engineers (India) & Former Director-Professor & Head Sanitary Engineering Department, All India Institute of Hygiene & Public Health.

Dr Mandira Ghosh

Assistant Teacher, Beliaghata Deshbandhu Girls High School (H.S.) & Former Research Scholar, Jadavpur University.

ABSTRACT

Over the millennium river Ganga has provided life support to around one-third of the population of India. The river has played an important role in sustaining and enforcing the cultural, social and religious traditions of large population residing in Ganga basin. However, ecological integrity of river ecosystem is facing threat from various kinds of technological interventions, such as, construction of dams and barrages hydro-electric projects etc. Loss of biodiversity has been observed in the river over the past many decades. Riverine ecosystem accordingly needs restoration through different planned activities so as to achieve continuous flow in the river, improvement in the quality of river water, protection of geological features and protection of aquatic biodiversity.

Key words: *River Ecosystem, Ecological Flow, Pollution, biodiversity.*

INTRODUCTION AND KEY ISSUES

River Ganga is the longest river (2525 KM) and Ganga Basin is the largest river system in the Indian sub continent. The river flows from Goumukh in Uttarakhand to the Bay of Bengal at Ganga Sagar in West Bengal covering 26% of India's landmass. The GPS location of river Ganga indicates as : at

Gongotri Glacier (Ganga source point) – 30.7983° N & 79.1642° E; and at Gangasagar (Ganga end point) – 21.6327° N & 88.0708° E. Catchment area of Ganga lies between East Longitudes 73° 30' to 89° 0' and North Latitudes 22° 30' to 31° 30'. Vast plains of fertile land and rich biodiversity are the assets of Ganga Basin facilitating sustenance of about 540 million of Indian population. Ecological integrity of the river ecosystem confronted to threat from various kinds of technical interventions in the form of construction of dams, barrages, hydroelectric projects etc during second half of twentieth century and first decade of twenty first century. Deterioration of riverine ecosystem through human interventions, such as, changes of land use pattern, tree cutting / deforestation, urbanization, industrialization etc has caused adverse impact on river Ganga. Unlike other ecosystems, the river ecosystems have unusually high permeable boundaries, importing and exporting matter, energy and organisms⁽¹⁾.

Significant loss of species biodiversity in the Ganga river network has been observed over the past many decades with many important aquatic species (fishes, dolphins, gharials, turtles etc) having dwindled or disappeared from river stretches in recent history⁽²⁾. In Ganga river basin, riverine resources are over-exploited and land-use pattern are considerably changed. Aquatic wildlife of the Ganga basin is under threat due to reduction of ecological flow and water level, pollution and over-exploitation of riverine resources. Restoration of ecosystem function in streams and rivers clearly requires to be looked beyond the banks, to the quality of the riparian and perhaps the entire landscape that meets special needs of individual species⁽¹⁾.

Another important issue is increasing dependence of groundwater resulting in increasing abstraction of groundwater in Ganga river basin for use in agriculture and industrial sectors and also for public water supply. This situation has caused lowering of groundwater table and adverse impact on the water resources in Ganga basin.

During early 80s of last century deterioration of Ganga river quality was detected and assessed to identify the sources of pollution. River quality assessment indicated that pollution loads received by river Ganga from point sources and non point sources of pollution are 75 to 77% and 23 to 25% respectively. Two distinct phenomenon were observed due to deterioration of riverine ecosystem are reduction of ecological flow in river and deterioration of water quality.

Point sources of pollution of river Ganga are (a) disposal of untreated or partially treated sewage/sullage from municipal cities / towns (b) disposal of untreated or partially

treated industrial effluent (c) disposal of untreated septage in outfall drains / canals leading to the river. Non- point sources of pollution of the river are (a) surface runoff carrying pesticides, insecticides and agricultural wastes; (b) disposal of municipal mixed solid waste (c) cattle shed waste disposal (d) mixing of wash-water of clothes (e) mass bathing (f) disposal of left out portion after religious performances (g) dumping of dead bodies both human and animal.

METHODOLOGY

Activities for abatement of pollution of river Ganga started in the year 1985 by launching Ganga Action Plan, Phase I. Different activities for cleaning up of the river are continuing till date by (a) laying intercepting sewers for diverting dry weather flow (sewage/sullage) and installing sewage treatment plants; (b) laying of sewerage network in several cities / towns for conveying sewage and installation of sewage

treatment plants; (c) carrying out river front development works including up-gradation of bathing ghats; (d) construction of community and public toilets (e) installation of electric crematoriums.

In order to restore riverine ecosystem, activities relating to watershed management and plantation will be necessary to facilitate higher recharging of groundwater. In addition rejuvenation and restoration of water bodies and wetlands in Ganga river basin will pave the way for the resilient riverine ecosystem. Installation of huge number of hydro-power projects and construction of dams and barrages has caused adverse impact on Ganga river ecosystem. The National Mission for Clean Ganga (NMCG) has stated its vision in terms of four river restoration pillars, namely Aviral Dhara (continuous flow), Nirmal Dhara (clean water), Geological Entity (protection of geological features) and Ecological Entity (protection of aquatic biodiversity). The methodology adopted by

NMCG along with the partnership of all relevant States and different stakeholders including academic institutions, NGOs etc in restoring river ecosystem inspite of all challenges is no doubt appropriate and unique under present socio-economic condition.

River ecosystem with its intrinsic biodiversity plays a crucial role in the functional health of the river basin and the ecosystem services provided by the river (2). Activities relating to restoration of Ganga river ecosystem need strict surveillance and monitoring on regular basis. Improvement in ecosystem requires to be assessed by analyzing different environmental parameters, water quality, river flow, biodiversity highlighting different species, increase in population of fishes, dolphins, ghariyals, turtles etc. Support and services of educational and research institutions require be sought for performance monitoring and assessment of the extent and magnitude of ecosystem restoration.

KEY FINDINGS

NMCG is initiated with a comprehensive approach to champion the challenges posed to Ganga through four different sectors, namely, waste water management, solid waste management, industrial pollution control and river front development. It has developed a comprehensive strategy to restore the biodiversity value of the Ganga-River with the ultimate goal to achieve the NMCG long term vision for Ganga River conservation so that viable population of all endemic and endangered aquatic species occupy their full historic range and fulfill their role in maintaining the integrity of the Ganga river ecosystem (3).

The Ganga river water quality is showing improvement and as a result many stretches of the river is now fit for bathing. Water quality improvement highlights reduction of BOD, increase of dissolved oxygen and decreasing trend of faecal coliform. River front development, bathing ghat renovation and up-gradation are showing encouraging social acceptance and people's participation in Namame Ganga program. In many river

stretches aquatic flora and fauna are getting restored. Certain activities in the river basin, such as, plantation, social forestry, afforestation, and water shed management have been taken up for river eco-system

Ganga Basin is home to a variety of relic, rare and threatened species. These include the Gangetic Dolphin (*Platanista gangetica*), three species of Otters viz, the Smooth Coated Otter (*Lutrogale perspicillata*), Eurasian Otter (*Lutra Lutra*) and the Small Clawed Otter (*Aonyx cinereus*), the critically Endangered Gharial (*Garialis gangeticus*), Mugger or Indian Marsh Crocodil (*Crocodylus palustris*), Estuarine Crocodil (*Crocodylus porosus*) and atleast 12 species of fresh-water turtles, including the Critically Endangered Batagur Kachuga within the Ganga river system, 143 different fresh water fish species belonging to 11 orders, 32 families and 72 genera have been reported including Critically Endangered Ganges Shark (*Glyphis gangeticus*), Gangetic Stingray (*Himantura fluviatilis*), Golden Mahseer (*Tor putitora*) and Hilsa (*Tenualosa ilisha*)⁽³⁾.

POLICY PERSPECTIVE & RECOMMENDATIONS

- Holistic approach must be taken for restoration of longitudinal connectivity along with maintenance of ecological flows and sediments throughout the Ganga river network. There is a need to have a policy to review the impact of existing hydro-power projects in the upper range of Ganga as well restriction
- on the installation of new projects.
- Activities are to be strengthened for restoration of unpolluted flow in the river by anthropogenic pollution. More stress should be given for abatement of point sources and non-point sources of pollution. Pollution load in the river from left out Ganga Towns shall be prevented by laying sewerage network and sewage treatment plants (STPS) or by

interception and diversion of sewage / sullage and treatment in STPs. There must be provision of faecal sludge management system in the entire river basin. Urban local bodies and industries should be encouraged for recycling and reuse of treated liquid. Industries shall be encouraged for achieving zero liquid discharge (ZLD) status.

- There must be restriction on alteration of river morphology.
- Control of over-fishing and fishing during spawning seasons shall be ensured.
- Water-shed management shall be encouraged in Ganga river basin with emphasis on reduction of groundwater abstraction.
- Urban river-front development should be taken up as per guidelines.

- As development and installation of Biodiversity Park is a unique concept for maintaining sustainable aquatic flora and fauna in the river and flood plain, activities are to be initiated for installation Biodiversity Parks in selected locations along the river.

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**INSTITUTION OF PUBLIC HEALTH ENGINEERS, INDIA (IPHE)
ANNUAL GENERAL MEETING
17th NOVEMBER, 2024, KOLKATA**

Presidential Address by Dr. Dinesh Chand

Dear Distinguished Corporate Members, Esteemed Council Colleagues, and Respected Guests,

Warm salutations to all of you in the aftermath of the recent celebratory period! I trust this communication finds you in good health and rejuvenated.

To commence, I deeply appreciate the opportunity to assume the role of President of our esteemed Institution. The confidence vested in me is a privilege, and I am privileged to lead an organization that epitomizes such a profound commitment to engineering excellence, public service, and community well-being. I wish to express my heartfelt gratitude to my fellow Council members and office bearers for their rock solid support since April 2023. Their dedication has empowered me to discharge my duties, and I am thankful for their collaboration, sagacity, and encouragement.

I would also like to extend my gratitude to our esteemed senior members, whose lasting influence continues to illuminate our path. A special acknowledgment is due to the late Prof. K. J. Nath, our immediate past President, late Shri S. K. Neogi, founder members, and late Dr. Bindeshwar Pathak, an Honorary Member, whose unwavering guidance and support have been invaluable. Their indelible contributions have profoundly impacted our Institution, whose absence is keenly felt occasionally. We also honour the memory of other senior members who have departed this year, leaving behind a rich legacy of wisdom, dedication, and influence.

As constituents of this Institution, it is our responsibility and honour to enhance the

reputation and contributions of the public health engineering community, particularly in the realms of public health and environmental services. In today's world, we are confronted with an unparalleled array of public health and environmental challenges. From the far-reaching effects of climate change impacting entire continents to localized issues affecting our communities, the imperative for action has never been more urgent. These challenges extend beyond the purview of public health and environmental engineers; they encompass the entire engineering community. It is incumbent upon us to actively immerse ourselves in comprehending, alleviating, and addressing these issues, leading the charge with expertise, proficiency, and ingenuity.

Beyond addressing these issues in our professional capacity, we carry the responsibility to foster awareness and inspire action within our communities. Public understanding is crucial to creating lasting change, and as experts and advocates, we must bridge the gap between technical solutions and community needs.

1. Engage with local schools and community centres to educate the public on environmental issues and sustainable practices.
2. Organize workshops and seminars to empower individuals to take action in their daily lives, from reducing waste to supporting renewable energy initiatives.
3. Collaborate with local governments to advocate for policies that promote a greener, more sustainable future for all community members.

4. Utilize social media platforms and online resources to amplify our message and reach a wider audience, encouraging collective action for a healthier planet.
5. Foster a sense of environmental stewardship and responsibility within our communities, emphasizing the importance of preserving natural resources for future generations.

Reflecting on our accomplishments, I am delighted to announce the successful conclusion of current year. The Annual Report presented by the Secretary-General underscores the fervor and participation of our members nationwide Regional Centres in metropolises such as Kolkata, Delhi, Bangalore, Agartala, Bhubaneswar, and Guwahati orchestrated vibrant events to honor this significant milestone.

To fortify these connections, I urge all corporate members in these regions to actively participate and revitalize their Regional Centres. With guidance from headquarters and senior members, we can invigorate local activities and improve coordination. I suggest that each Council member maintain close communication with a specific regional centre to nurture engagement. The Secretary-General and Secretaries supervised the implementation of this plan to ensure that every Regional Centre has a robust support network. Furthermore, I propose establishing Ad hoc Committees for Centres where elected Executive Committees are presently inactive or missing, under our By-laws.

Building Capacity and Expanding Skills

Our Institution harbours an exceptional reservoir of expertise in the fields of Public Health and Environmental Engineering. This collective wealth of knowledge is not only a valuable asset but also a profound responsibility—to harness it for the advancement of skills, enhancement of community living standards, and provision of

technical assistance for the planning, execution, and supervision of public health and environmental infrastructure.

I call upon the Executive Committees and Ad hoc Committees of each Regional Centre to commence training programs commencing in 2025. These programs should cater to engineers, technicians, technical support staff, and students, with financial assistance sought from state and central governments, as well as semi-government and non-government funding agencies. The Headquarters is prepared to offer the necessary logistical and technical support. Let us motivate each Centre to undertake these initiatives, nurturing the skills required for a sustainable future and igniting the passion in the upcoming generation of engineering talent.

Addressing Financial Challenges and Enhancing Resource Mobilization Moving on to a crucial matter—the financial status of our Institution. As outlined by the Treasurer in the Audited Accounts, we are confronting a shortfall that has regrettably led to the liquidation of fixed deposits. This predicament has persisted over the years and demands immediate, unified action to safeguard our financial well-being.

To tackle this issue, I call upon all corporate members to contribute towards mobilizing resources. This may involve securing advertisements for the IPHE Journal, Newsletter, and various Souvenirs published by HQ, as well as acquiring funding for study or training projects. Moreover, donations to the IPHE Development Fund and Building Fund will fortify our foundation. Membership recruitment drives also remain crucial, as they aid in broadening our outreach and financial support. I encourage Regional Centres to enhance their financial well-being through active participation in IPHE activities, and I suggest the incorporation of QR codes and mobile payment options to facilitate seamless online donations and transfers.

Focusing on Key Strategic Priorities

I would like to underscore several critical priorities highlighted in the reports from our Secretary General, Secretaries, and Treasurer:

1. **Updating the Constitution:** Incorporate all amendment proposals approved by the General Body into the Memorandum of Association and Bye-Laws, ensuring alignment with our mission and legal requirements.
2. **Publications:** Maintaining the high standards of our Journal and Newsletter is vital, and I encourage all members to contribute quality technical articles. Council members and Office bearers must support HQ in ensuring regular publication and distribution in print format, made possible through accurate and up-to-date contact information from our members.
3. **Infrastructure Improvements:** The installation of a lift in the IPHE HQ building, funded by the late Dr. Bindeshwar Pathak, is a priority, and we aim to complete it at the earliest to improve accessibility to all floors.
4. **Student Membership Drive:** Initiated by the Delhi Regional Centre, this drive will encourage emerging engineers to join our Institution. I urge all Regional Centres to support this initiative, as it will nurture future public health and environmental engineering leaders.
5. **Enhanced Digital Presence:** Currently, our digital presence is limited to our website and WhatsApp groups. Expanding our outreach to platforms like 'X' (formerly Twitter), YouTube, Facebook, and Instagram will allow us to engage more effectively with the broader engineering community and beyond.
6. **IPHE Council election:** The IPHE Council election has already been declared. I appeal to all the members to participate actively in the forthcoming IPHE Council election process and also opt for an e-voting option. Similarly,

Regional centres should also follow the election process as and when due to maintain the democratic framework of the Institution.

Closing Remarks

In conclusion, I earnestly urge Council members and all corporate associates to persist in their unwavering commitment to our Institution, mirroring the steadfast dedication demonstrated in previous years. Let us collaboratively strive to revitalize IPHE to its illustrious past, fortifying its influence both domestically and globally, specifically within the realms of Public Health and Environmental Engineering.

As we gaze towards the future, let us bear in mind that our endeavours wield a profound influence on societies, the natural world, and the forthcoming generations. Collectively, we have the capacity to cultivate ingenuity, tenacity, and durability in the realm of engineering—principles that will propel IPHE toward a luminous and consequential future.

I extend my heartfelt wishes for a joyful and prosperous New Year in 2025 to you and your loved ones.

Long live the Institute of Public Health Engineering (IPHE) Jai Hind!

Dr. Dinesh Chand

Enrol as a member of IPHE

1. Get 4 issues of quarterly journal free.
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3. Further the activities of the Institution.
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INSTITUTION OF PUBLIC HEALTH ENGINEERS, INDIA
ANNUAL GENERAL MEETING: 2023-2024
17th November, 2024 at IPHE Hq. Building

Secretary General's Annual Report

Mr. President, Vice President, Members of IPHE and invited Guests.

I welcome you this morning to this august gathering and place before you the Annual Report of IPHE for the year 2023-2024. During the year in question, we had lost a few of our esteemed members who enriched IPHE through their experience and wisdom. We remember them dearly and our respects to the departed souls. We also share the grief and sorrow with the families of the departed members. Let us observe one minute's Silence to pay our respect to the departed souls.

During the year in question the following numbers of Corporates Members enrolled themselves:

Fellow Member – 20
 Member - 24
 Associate Member – 6

Coming to the financial scenario of the Institution, the year 2023-2024 was somewhat better compared to the previous year. While the details of the Accounts for the year in question will be presented by our Treasurer, it may be summarily mentioned that the financial deficit for the year was of the order of Rs. 1,64,000/- (approx.) as against Rs. 10,47,000/- (approx.) for the year 2022-2023. This indicates considerable recovery in the financial condition from the previous year. However, we are continuing to restrict expenditure strictly by adopting austerity measures as much as possible to achieve a positive financial balance in the year 2024-2025.

IPHE had conducted CPHEEO sponsored

Refresher Courses in Public Health Engineering for three consecutive years (2016-2017, 2017-2018 & 2018-2019) for which reimbursement of course conducting fee of 1,83,532/- still remains unpaid. During the year 2023-2024, we had taken all efforts as suggested by CPHEEO & Ministry of Urban Development, GoI but the reimbursement could not be obtained.

Installation of a lift in IPHE Building has been a priority issue and during 2023-2024 the committee constituted for installation of lift in this building has considered various options for the work. It was finally decided that the lift will be installed in the location as shown in the revised sanctioned plan of the building. The validity of sanction of the revised plan, however, needs extension from Bidhannagar Municipal Corporation.

The Annual General Meeting of the Institution for 2022-2023 was held on Sunday the 26th November, 2023 at IPHE Building. 65 Corporate Members attended the meeting (physically and virtually).

During the year 2023-2024, IPHE organised the following events:

- Popular talk on 25th November, 2023 by Er. Chandan Sengupta in the Auditorium of the IPHE Headquarters office. The theme of the popular talk: "Management of Bio-degradable Waste at Household level"
- National Seminar on 15th -16th March, 2024 in Hotel Stadel. The Theme of the National Seminar was "Sustainable Urban Water & Waste Management through Good Governance"

- Observance of World Water Day, 2024 on 23rd March, 2024.
- Observance of World Environment Day on 3rd June, 2023 in the Auditorium of the IPHE Headquarters office. The theme of World Environment Day 2023 was "Beat Plastic Pollution". On the same day IPHE also observed the concluding function of Golden Jubilee Celebration of IPHE.
- ◆ Bhubaneswar Regional Centre virtually organised Hiroshima Day 2023 on 6th August, 2023.
- ◆ World Nature Conservation Day, 2023 was organised on 28th July, 2023 by Bangalore Regional Centre in association with Dayananda Sagar College of Engineering virtually.
- ◆ World Population Day, 2023 was observed on 11th July, 2023 jointly hosted by Agartala and Delhi Regional Centre.

The Regional Centres of the Institution during the year 2023-2024 also organised the following events

- ◆ Agartala Regional Centre in collaboration with Urban Development Department, govt. of Tripura and Tripura Jal Board organised a seminar in observance of world Environment Day, 2024.
- ◆ Bangalore Regional Centre organised World Environment Day, 2024 in collaboration with IE (India), Karnataka State Centre.
- ◆ Bangalore Regional Centre organised Engineers day, 2023 on 15th September, 2023 jointly with IWWA and Dayananda Sagar College of Engineering and Indian Concrete Institute.
- ◆ Agartala Regional Centre organised Engineers day, 2023 on 15th September, 2023 jointly with urban Development department, Govt. of Tripura and Tripura Jal Board.

Sri K A Roy, Secretary, IPHE Headquarters office during the year 2023-2024 visited Agartala, Guwahati and Delhi Regional Centres for interaction with the members and rejuvenation of the Centres. Besides, different Office Bearers / representatives of Kerala, Bangaluru, Bhubaneswar, Agra and Agartala Centres visited the Headquarters office during the year.

I take this opportunity of thanking the President and all the Council Members for extending their help and co-operation. Special mention for discharge of functioning of IPHE must be made about the service of the Office Assistants for all their secretarial assistance.

I thank all the members of IPHE and pray for their and their families good health and wellbeing.

NOTICE

Corporate Members and all concerned are requested to send technical articles for the Journal of the Institution (JIPHE) and also updated information about membership including change of address and contact details by email to eipheindia@gmail.com only.

All other communication may kindly be made by email to iphe.india@gmail.com.

Secretary General
IPHE

OUR MEMBERS

Corporate members of IPHE (I) are requested to send News about their achievements (promotion, new job, foreign assignment, new areas of activities, special honours, scholarships etc.) for publication in the '**Members**' News' column. Matters within 100 words should be sent to the Editor.

Organisation members of IPHE (I) are requested to send **news** about their achievements (diversification, new project obtained, new research work done, special awards and the like) for publication in the '**Members**' News' column. Matters within 100 words should be sent to the Editor.

Members Elected

The following persons with details mentioned against each was elected Corporate Members during 2024-2025.

Sl No.	Name and Address	Membership No.
16.	Dr. Raktim Biswas 'Shyamali', Arobindopally, SP More, P.O.: Suri, Birbhum – 731101 Mob & Whatsapp: 8116160310 Email: raktim.biswas6215@gmail.com	LM 1727 <i>Upgraded from LAM – 777</i>
17.	Ardhendu Datta Rabindra Pally, Near Red Cross Primary School Suri – 731101 Mob & Whatsapp: 9832273933 Email: dattaardhendu14@gmail.com	LM 1728
18.	Arpan Karmakar B-1, Nandankanan, Santoshpur, Kolkata – 700075 Mob: 9477322477 Email: arpank9477@gmail.com	LM 1729
19.	Dr. Swapan Bhaumik Dangal Para, Suri, Near Kaligati School, Birbhum – 731101 Mob & Whatsapp No.: 9475986145	LM 1730
20.	Ankita Dutta Shivam Abasan, Malakarpara, South Station Road, Agarpara – 700109 Mob & Whatsapp: 8910888912 Email: ankitadutta291@gmail.com	LAM 817

Engineers whose names are shown in Sl. No. 16 to 18 were elected in Council Meeting No. 03 / 2024-2025 held on 24.08.2024 at Kolkata.

Engineers whose names are shown in Sl. No. 19 & 20 were elected in Council Meeting No. 04 / 2024-2025 held on 19.10.2024 at Kolkata.

We cordially welcome the elected member in the IPHE fraternity, and look forward to member's keen interest and whole hearted participation in the activities to further the cause of IPHE.

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